

Dicoma capensis

Fever bush

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© N. van Berkel

Group: Eudicot

Size: 30 to 60 cm

Distribution:

The Fever bush occurs in the western parts of southern Africa, in Namibia, Botswana, and South Africa, where plants occur in the Free State, Northern Cape, Western Cape, and Eastern Cape. They are commonly found growing on rocky hills in sandy soils or calcrete.

Importance:

Eaten by insects and pollinated by bees, *Dicoma capensis* is used in traditional medicine to treat colds, fever, back pain, haemorrhoids, bladder infections, kidney problems, influenza, nausea, liver problems, stomach problems, diarrhea, and rheumatism, and as a bitter tonic.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 55.85 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.79 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.67 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 98.6%, Duplicated: 1.2%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 48 492.12 kilobases

Contig number: 684

Sample Contributor contact details:

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